

INVESTIGATION OF THE EMOTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF WHITE FOR DESIGNING WHITE BASED PRODUCTS

Noo-Ree Na, Geun-Ly Park, Hyeon-Jeong Suk

Department of Industrial Design, KAIST

nooree427@kaist.ac.kr, geunli@kaist.ac.kr, h.j.suk@kaist.ac.kr

ABSTRACT

In this study we investigated emotional characteristics of various shades of whites which have slightly different nuances to suggest guidelines that will help designers to select the appropriate colors when designing white based product. The study involved three different procedures. In Experiment 1, we selected 20 emotional words through a survey (N=30) among 60 words, which we picked from literature review and workshop and was thought to be appropriate to evaluate product colors. In Experiment 2, we evaluated the emotions of 13 basic colors from the I.R.I Hue&Tone 120 system (N=30) using the 20 previously selected emotional words, to find relative emotional positions of white in comparison to other colors. Finally, in Experiment 3, we conducted an emotional evaluation on various shades of whites using the extracted factors. The color stimuli used in each of the three experiments were measured in terms of CIE 1976 L*a*b color space. Throughout the three empirical studies, we observed three overruling tendencies : First, there are four important factors when evaluating product color – flamboyant, elegant, clear and soft; second, white is dominantly the most elegant in comparison to other colors; third, every emotional factor of the study was affected by hue, saturation and brightness.

Keywords : white products, product color, color emotion, emotional word, color evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

It is well-known that color significantly affects human emotions and feelings (Hemphill, 1996). Every color

has its own characteristics, and each color induces different feelings. As an example, red is associated with exciting and stimulating emotions, while blue is associated with secure and comfortable feelings, and yellow with cheerful and joyful feelings (Wexner, 1954). Among these diverse colors, white has particularly distinct characteristics. First, white is the standard point of every color. The standard of all colors can be changed based on the white point. For instance, there is a color difference in plain paper between Korea and Japan. Both papers are basically white, but papers that are made in Korea have a tinge of blue whereas papers that are made in Japan are yellowish. This difference in the white can be a result of the different 'perception of white' between the Korean and Japanese. Moreover, white is the most universally used color in all industries. White has been ranked as the most popular vehicle color in the world (PPG industries, 2011), and most home appliances are painted by white bases. A reason for this widespread use of white may be because white exudes a positive impression, reminding users of clean, pure, refreshing, beautiful, gentle and natural sentiments (Saito, 1996).

White is the brightest color and it does not have hue. Also, it is easily changeable by add some color. Therefore, a deep understanding of white expands the perception of white color to designers (Park, 2009). However, the color we refer to as 'white' is not in fact a single color. There are many colors which are white-based but have slightly different nuances – some whites are yellowish and more saturated and some other whites are bluish and have lower brightness, and these varying whites have their own respective emotional characteristics. In this study, we attempt to

understand the emotional characteristics of various whites. Furthermore, we intend to provide design guidelines to select the appropriate product colors that truly convey the desired emotion when designing white based product. We hypothesize that each color has its respective emotional characteristics, and this is largely controlled by the hue, saturation and brightness of color.

GOAL

The goal of this study is to find the appropriate emotional factors to evaluate product color, and investigate the emotional characteristics of various whites that have slightly different nuances. We will examine the affection of hue, saturation, brightness to understand what causes the different emotions for different shades of white colors.

EXPERIMENT PLAN

In studying the emotional characteristics of various shade of whites, we conducted three experiments. First, we selected emotional words that are suited to evaluate product colors through survey. Then we evaluated 13 basic colors from the I.R.I Hue & Tone 120 system using the selected emotional words in previous experiment. Finally, in order to obtain the detailed results on white, we conducted an emotional evaluation for various whites.

PRIOR STUDY TO DEFINE RANGE OF WHITE

Before experiments, we conducted prior study to define the perceptual range of white in daily life. Eight colors (yellow, yellow red, red, red blue, blue, blue green, green, green yellow) with S 5% in NCS Color System were selected as color stimuli, and we divided the brightness between each color and white to 12 levels. Participants (N=50) were asked to select a maximum permitted level that regarded as white color. As a result, average permitted level of L^* value in CIE 1976 $L^*a^*b^*$ was 92.53. Because of the color difference of L^* value that is current in daily life is ± 2 (CHROMiX, 2005), we defined white as the colors that have various hue and saturation within L^* value above 90.53 and below 94.53.

EXPERIMENT I

OBJECTIVE

Aim of Experiment I is extracting the appropriate adjectives that can be used to assess the emotional quality of color stimuli, which will later be used within Experiments II and Experiment III.

METHOD

Participants

A group of thirty people comprised of 14 male students and 16 female students participated in the online survey. The average age of the participants was 23.97 years old with a standard deviation of 2.09 years.

Stimuli words

We extracted 150 adjectives that represent emotions drawn by products through literature reviews (Kobayashi, 1990; Jeong & Lee, 2004). Then, through a design expert workshop, we narrowed down those 150 adjectives into 60 words. 5 design experts participated in workshop, and they eliminated extremely inappropriate words to express product color and deleted overlapped vocabularies. All adjectives were written in Korean.

Procedure

For Experiment I, participants were asked to evaluate how well the 60 adjectives conveyed the emotion induced by the product color. Participants had to gauge the suitability of the color based on the seven point Likert scale (7 point; very appropriate, 1 point; not appropriate).

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Before conducting the main analysis, we first processed a reliability test and the results showed very high inter-rater reliability. Based on the ratings of the survey, we conducted one sample T-test (target score; 4 point) with 60 adjectives and found that 29 of them were over 4 points and thus statistically significant. Because some of the 60 adjectives had similar meanings, we narrowed down the adjective list to 20 terms by grouping synonyms. Table 1 shows the results of the final 20 emotional word groups with their mean scores and standard deviations.

Luxurious (M=5.80, SD=1.52)	Weak (M=5.70, SD=1.56)	Cozy (M=5.67, SD=1.21) Soft (M=5.63, SD=1.27)	Fresh (M=5.67, SD=1.18)
Clear (M=5.60, SD=1.25) Clean (M=5.33, SD=1.56)	Neat (M=5.60, SD=1.35)	Flamboyant (M=5.57, SD=1.50)	Delicate (M=5.50, SD=1.63)
Calm (M=5.33, SD=1.32) Graceful (M=5.13, SD=1.38) Mild (M=4.67, SD=1.40)	Light (M=5.33, SD=1.65) Weighty (M=5.07, SD=1.86)	Stand out (M=5.27, SD=1.57) Impressive (M=4.77, SD=1.45)	Cheerful (M=5.20, SD=1.58)
Elegant (M=5.13, SD=1.50) Noble (M=4.97, SD=1.96) Dignified (M=4.83, SD=1.56)	Sensuous (M=5.13, SD=1.28)	Lovely (M=5.13, SD=1.25)	Sophisticated (M=5.00, SD=1.29) Modern (M=4.77, SD=1.19)
Cute (M=4.97, SD=1.83)	Classic (M=4.93, SD=1.44)	Charming (M=4.87, SD=1.61)	Comfortable (M=4.77, SD=1.43)

Table 1. 20 Emotional adjective groups for evaluating product color (N=30, 7 point Likert scale)

DISCUSSION

Experiment I revealed that certain emotional words are more appropriate for evaluating product color than others. For instance, 'luxurious' had the highest score and adjectives such as 'weak', 'cozy' and 'fresh' scored high as well. This implies that these words are most appropriate for expressing the emotion of product color. Next, in order to extract the factors of color emotion, we conducted Experiment II.

EXPERIMENT II

OBJECTIVE

We planned to extract the emotional factors of product color using the word groups from Experiment I. By coupling basic colors with emotional factors, we tried to examine the relative emotional characteristic of white in comparison to other colors.

METHOD

Participants

We recruited a group of 30 people comprised of 16 male students and 14 female students and whose average age was 23.60 years old with a standard deviation of 2.63 years. The proportion of design majors to non-design majors was almost half.

Stimuli

We prepared 3cm by 3cm color patches taken from I.R.I Hue & Tone 120 System. As shown in Table 2, we used ten hues in vivid tones (from Red to Red

Purple) and the three neutral colors, white, gray and black – total 13 colors. Participants were provided with color stimuli in a random order.

Color	Munsell Hue	Tone	Code of I.R.I Hue & Tone System
	5R (red)	V (vivid)	5R/V
	5YR (yellow red)	V (vivid)	5YR/V
	5Y (yellow)	V (vivid)	5Y/V
	5GY (green yellow)	V (vivid)	5GY/V
	5G (green)	V (vivid)	5G/V
	5BG (blue green)	V (vivid)	5BG/V
	5B (blue)	V (vivid)	5B/V
	5PB (purple blue)	V (vivid)	5PB/V
	5P (purple)	V (vivid)	5P/V
	5RP (red purple)	V (vivid)	5RP/V
	N9.5 (white)	N (neutral)	N9.5
	N6 (gray)	N (neutral)	N6
	N1.5 (black)	N (neutral)	N1.5

Table 2. 13 color stimuli for Experiment II extracted from I.R.I Hue & Tone 120 System

Procedure

For Experiment II, participants were asked to evaluate 13 colors using 20 emotional word groups based on the 7-point Likert scale. For instance, we asked them to give a score of 7 points if they strongly agreed with the coupling between the given color and the presented emotional word.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The reliability test (every alpha value was above 0.80) on the 13 colors, showed that there were significant differences- KMO was over 0.80, Bartlett’s significant value was less than 0.05. We proceeded with a factor analysis to extract emotional factors to evaluate product color. Only the Eigen values higher than 1, giving a cumulative variance above 66.39% were retained. As a result we identified four emotional factors. Table 3 shows the four extracted factors and this can serve as the explanation to 66.39% of data. The words included in factor 1 are flamboyant, stand out/ impressive, lovely, charming, sensuous and cute. We named this factor as ‘flamboyant’. The following factors were titled as ‘elegant’, ‘clear’ and ‘soft’.

no.	factor label	included items
1	How flamboyant is it? (not ~ very much)	flamboyant, stand out/impressive, lovely, charming, sensuous, cute
2	How elegant is it? (not ~ very much)	luxurious, modern/sophisticated, elegant/noble/dignified, neat, classic, graceful/mild/calm
3	How clear is it? (not ~ very much)	clean/clear, light, fresh, cheerful, weak
4	How soft is it? (not ~ very much)	delicate, soft/cozy, comfortable

Table 3. The results of factor analysis, Experiment II (N=30)

By calculating the mean score of each color and positioning them on a 2-dimensional graph of two dominant factors ‘flamboyant’ and ‘elegant’, we obtained the emotional characteristics of basic colors. Generally, as shown in Figure 1, warm colors seem to be regarded as more flamboyant than cold colors. Neutral colors (black and gray) obtained very low scores within the ‘flamboyant’ factor. However, white is superior to other colors in terms of the ‘elegant’ factor so it is located far away from the others.

DISCUSSION

We were able to observe an emotional tendency across the basic colors. Generally, warm colors are regarded to be more flamboyant, whereas gray and black are not so. Among the basic colors, white is dominantly viewed as elegant. These findings support the hypothesis that there is a similar tendency across the varying nuances of white. So we proceeded with Experiment III, which provided color patches in various whites.

Figure 1. The emotional characteristics of 13 colors plotted in a two-dimensional space profiled with ‘flamboyant’ horizontally and ‘elegant’ vertically, Experiment II (N=30)

EXPERIMENT III

OBJECTIVE

As mentioned above, Experiment III was an extension of Experiment II, which studied the various shades of white. We examined the different emotional responses based on the different whites and tried to quantify these discrepancies in terms of hue, saturation and brightness.

METHOD

Participants

Thirty people comprising of 13 male students and 17 female students participated in the experiment and their average age was 23.33 years old with a standard deviation of 3.24 years. All subjects were paid

volunteers, and students without color vision problems were selected.

Stimuli

As shown in Table 4, we prepared 25 white color patches in various nuances taken from the NCS color system and three anchor patches - white, gray and black taken from the I.R.I Hue & Tone 120 system. Among the 25 patches, there was one neutral color patch and the rest had eight hues (yellow, yellow red, red, red blue, blue, blue green, green, green yellow) with three saturations. The anchor colors were embedded to compare the result with the previous experiment. We measured the CIE 1976 L*a*b* value of the color patches using spectrophotometer (CM-2600d) in order to analyze the result quantitatively.

Hue category	Chroma level	CIE 1976 L*a*b*			Code
		L*	a*	b*	
yellow	high	92.63	-1.15	5.35	Y/H
yellow red	high	91.60	2.17	3.70	YR/H
red	high	91.48	3.27	1.72	R/H
red blue	high	92.47	2.12	-1.96	RB/H
blue	high	91.02	-0.44	-2.78	B/H
blue green	high	91.33	-2.85	-2.35	BG/H
green	high	91.88	-3.9	1.01	G/H
green yellow	high	91.76	-3.63	5.65	GY/H
yellow	medium	92.43	-0.41	4.65	Y/M
yellow red	medium	91.70	3.09	4.03	YR/M
red	medium	92.17	2.78	1.55	R/M
red blue	medium	92.25	1.79	-1.49	RB/M
blue	medium	90.89	-0.53	-1.8	B/M
blue green	medium	91.79	-2.74	-1.34	BG/M
green	medium	91.66	-3.02	0.84	G/M
green yellow	medium	91.74	-3.27	4.19	GY/M
yellow	low	91.36	-1.03	5.07	Y/L
yellow red	low	91.83	3.36	5.45	YR/L
red	low	91.44	2.28	1.10	R/L
red blue	low	91.69	3.53	-2.67	RB/L
blue	low	90.55	-0.67	-3.17	B/L
blue green	low	90.15	-2.34	-1.85	BG/L
green	low	91.68	-3.71	0.66	G/L
green yellow	low	90.73	-3.54	2.99	GY/L
neutral	-	91.46	-0.25	1.23	N
white	-	92.81	-0.72	0.76	White
gray	-	60.90	-0.82	-4.87	Gray
black	-	24.96	0.32	0.22	Black

Table 4. The color stimuli of Experiment III: 25 nuanced white colors and three achromatic colors, such as black, gray and white

Procedure

Participants were provided with the 28 stimuli in a random order, and they were asked to evaluate those colors with four emotional factors - 'flamboyant', 'elegant', 'clear' and 'soft' based on the 7 point scale.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

We conducted a reliability test on each emotional factor, and all of their Cronbach's alpha value shows that they were reliable (Cronbach's Alpha value: flamboyant: 0.84; elegant: 0.83; clear: 0.73; soft: 0.65). We positioned both 13 basic colors from Experiment II and all whites with their mean scores on a 2-dimensional graph of flamboyant and elegant factors. As is the case for the basic colors, various whites have their respective emotional characteristics according to their color nuances. As shown in Figure 2, the color white in warm color nuances were regarded as more flamboyant than cold and neutral color nuances. In order to analyze this distribution tendency, we conducted stepwise multiple regression analyses using the value of hue (a^* , b^*), brightness (L^*), and saturation ($C = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}$) as independent variables, and the result of emotional evaluation as dependent variable. a^* and b^* value which mean hue are chromaticity diagram, and they affect independently ($+a^*$: red, $-a^*$: green, $+b^*$: yellow, $-b^*$: blue). Saturation C is not independently affects because it is the result of interaction effect between a^* and b^* . However, it was included in the equation because the explanation capacity gets higher when C value is included as independent variable. By conducting multiple regression analyses, we figured out the effect of hue, saturation and brightness on emotional factors. The sense of a color being flamboyant is affected by hue and saturation. This means that colors with higher a^* and lower b^* value, higher C value are regarded as more flamboyant than other colors. The sentiment that a color is elegant is affected by the brightness and hue of a color. High brightness and a^* value, and low b^* value maximize the elegant feeling. Emotion of clear factor is affected by hue, saturation and brightness all together. A color becomes more clear with lower a^* and b^* value (e.g. cold color), and higher brightness and saturation. The sentiment that a color is soft is affected by hue,

saturation and brightness like clear emotion. The higher the brightness, saturation and a* value the more soft a color feels. When we see the color, we

can predict its emotional factors with the equation shown in Table 5 by putting its color value.

Figure 2. The emotional characteristics of 25 nuanced whites in comparison with those of 13 basic colors plotted in a two-dimensional space profiled with 'flamboyant' horizontally and 'elegant' vertically, Experiment III (N=30)

Emotion factor (scale: 1~7)	Color emotion equation using color value(L, a, b, C) - L, a, b C value is declaration method to express all product color by human vision - C (saturation) = $\sqrt{a^2+b^2}$	R ²	Sig.
flamboyant	0.4a-0.3b+0.56C	.76	.00**
elegant	0.18L+0.22a-0.09b-12.49	.69	.00**
clear	0.7L-0.16a-0.31b+0.3C-60.58	.68	.00**
soft	0.27L+0.09a+0.16C-20.42	.47	.01*

Table 5. Equation for calculating color emotion by using color value (L*, a*, b*, C)

DISCUSSION

We found similar emotional tendencies throughout various shades of whites and basic colors. As was the case with the basic colors, white in warm color nuances were regarded as more flamboyant than cold and neutral colors. We can predict the emotional responses to various whites with their CIE 1976

L*a*b* value. Whether or not a color is judged as flamboyant depends on the hue (a*, b*) and saturation (C). If a* and C value increase, and b* value decrease – in other words, in purplish and more saturated white, people feel more flamboyant emotion. Elegant emotion depends on the brightness (L*) and hue (a*, b*) of a color. The color with higher brightness level

and a^* value, and lower b^* value enhances those emotional characteristics. Whether a color is perceived as clear and soft are influenced by all color values – hue (a^* , b^* in clear, a^* in soft), saturation (C) and brightness (L^*). For example, white in highly saturated cold color (lower a^* , b^* value) with high brightness express strong feeling of clearness, whereas white in highly saturated red nuances (higher a^* value) with high brightness feels softer than other whites.

VALIDITY ANALYSIS OF COLOR EMOTION EQUATION

To confirm the suitability of the color emotion equation, we conducted a validity analysis using mobile phone mock-ups (Figure 3) that have same color as the color stimuli used in Experiment III. 80 participants were asked to choose one mock-up for each emotional factor which best presents the emotion. Flamboyant emotional value from the equation of mock-up that was most frequently selected as flamboyant product was 5.38. Elegant emotional value of the most frequently selected as elegant mock-up was 4.48. Clear and soft emotional values of the mock-ups that most well represent those feelings were 6.49 and 5.16. All of the selected mock-ups got relatively high scores in each emotion. This means that the result of color emotion equation is well matched with the actual emotional characteristics that people feel, so it is appropriate to apply as a product color.

Figure 3. mobile phone mock-ups for validity analysis

IMPLICATIONS FOR DESIGN PRACTICE

Using the result of this study - color emotion equation - we can predict the emotion of the colors. For example, there are two different whites – white A and white B. White A has yellow nuances and white B has a tinge of blue, as shown in Table 6. Then, we can

calculate and predict the emotional response for each color by substituting the respective color values (L^* , a^* , b^* , C) into the color emotion equation. The level of the 'elegant (A: 4.16, B: 4.18)' and 'soft (5.04, B: 4.57)' factors are similar. In the 'flamboyant' factor, white A (3.12) is more flamboyant than white B (1.01), but neither of them express flamboyant emotion much because they have quite low levels of hues. Also, in the 'clear' factor, white B has a markedly higher score, which means that if a designer wants to give an impression of clarity and softness to his or her product, white B should be used. Similarly, people can select the appropriate white color based on the type of emotion they wish to evoke.

GENERAL DISCUSSION

In this study, we attempted to extract appropriate emotional factors to evaluate product color and investigate the emotional characteristics of various whites with slightly different nuances. As a result of this study, we extracted 4 important emotional factors (flamboyant, elegant, clear, and soft). Also, we found that each white has its respective emotional characteristics that are affected by hue, saturation and brightness of color. These results support the hypothesis of this study. However, we should consider that white is markedly shifted to the elegant factor axis, and we focused on the domain of white. This means that although some whites get low scores in the elegant factor, it is comparatively more elegant than other colors, and if some whites get higher scores, then that specific white has to be dominantly elegant. Also, there is a similar tendency between basic colors and various shades of whites regarding the distribution in the two-dimensional emotional graph - warm colors are more flamboyant than cool and neutral colors. This is because participants adapt to white during evaluation, so they regard various shades of whites the same as basic colors that colors with a very high brightness value.

Color name	Color value			Color sample	Values on the emotion factor			
	L*	a*	b*		flamboyant (1~7)	elegant (1~7)	clear (1~7)	soft (1~7)
white A	90.91	3.07	5.37		3.12	4.16	2.93	5.04
white B	93.28	-1.49	-1.13		1.01	4.18	6.04	4.57

Table 6. Score of four emotional factors of white A and white B

White, gray and black colors were evaluated in both experiments but the results varied each time. However, distribution tendency is still similar, so we can assume that different color stimuli which are evaluated together can alter the evaluation responses provided by participants. Additionally, we confirmed the suitability of color emotion equation to product color through validity analysis using product mock-up. The limitation of this study is that experiment was done by only Korean students. However, the emotion of white color is regarded analogously all over the world – clean, pure and elegant - so this may not be a serious problem. The findings from the experiments can be applied when designer want to design white products with consideration to color emotion. The result of the color emotion equation is a majority opinion, so designers can refer to it when they make a decision compared to their own opinion. Most importantly, it can be said that this study is a

groundwork effort on drafting design guidelines that can evaluate diverse product colors.

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